

ACCURATE PREDICTION OF NOISE GENERATION AND PROPAGATION

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Abstract

Jet engines are characterized by high-speed free jets. The fact that Federal Aviation Regulations regarding noise levels retard the progress in high speed civil transport planes raises the interest in accurate methods to predict and reduce jet noise. Here, the perturbed flow field of a supersonic jet is solved using an advantageous numerical technique, and the associated noise field is predicted. Comparisons with experimental results show that this technique is efficient for this kind of problems as it gives accurate results without requiring a lot of computational power. Due to the nature of the problem, special attention needs to be given to the numerical method as well as the boundary treatments. We observed radial acoustic profiles at different axial distances, where peak intensity is encountered before the decay.

Introduction

The word 'sound' typically refers to audible pressure fluctuations in the ambient air. Audible pressure fluctuations can be generated by the vibrations of solid surfaces such as the vibrating strings of violins and harps, and the vibrating diaphragms of loudspeakers. They can also be generated as a result of fluid motion. The latter type is considered in the current study. Attempts toward noise prediction go back more than fifty years ago. Some early measurements of the intensity of far field noise from turbulent air jets were done by Morely (1939). Analytical, experimental, and numerical approaches have been used to assess flow noise. Analytical approaches include Lighthill's acoustic analogy, which yields prediction of jet noise if the source of the sound is known a priori. Detailed experimental measurements of the source and its retarded time would be very difficult. Numerical approaches include the use of linear stability theory, direct numerical simulation, large eddy simulation, and linearized Euler equations. Linear stability theory considers only instability modes. In direct numerical simulation, the full time-dependent, compressible Navier-Stokes equations governing both sound generation and propagation need to be solved. This method is not only very expensive in terms of computational costs, but also there is a possibility that the order of magnitude of the acoustic field is comparable to the numerical errors of the resolved field. There are few reported studies where this approach was used to predict noise, such as the study conducted by Freund et al. (1998) who applied this technique to study a perfectly expanded supersonic turbulent jet. They solved the compressible Navier-Stokes equations in cylindrical coordinates in a computational domain that included the near acoustic field. The simulations were conducted for cold jet. Freund (1999) applied direct numerical simulation to study a subsonic jet and its radiated sound. The calculated pressure field was used to compute the Lighthill acoustic source. Good agreement was reported between the Lighthill's analogy and the directly computed sound field. The large eddy simulation is another numerical technique with less computational demands than the direct numerical simulation. In this technique, the flow field is decomposed into large-scales and small-scales (also called subgrid scales), both are time-dependent. The former is captured directly whereas the

latter is modeled. The noise generated by the small-scale components is not captured. Also, there is still fear that the acoustic field is blurred by the numerical errors involved in the calculations of the flow variables, as in the direct numerical simulation case. Bodony and Lele (2006) reported a good review of the current status of jet noise predictions using large eddy simulation, considering both subsonic and supersonic jets. In the current study, the linearized Euler equations are solved using high-order finite difference scheme to compute the perturbed field for a supersonic jet. The associated acoustic field is calculated and analyzed at different locations in the domain. Special attention is paid to the used numerical method and the boundary treatment in order to have accurate results. This method was chosen to prove its suitability for engineering problems as it provides reasonably accurate results and in the same time does not require high computational power.

Numerical Method

The perturbed flow is modeled by the linearized Euler equations, which is a linearized form of the full nonlinear Euler equations about the mean flow variable. In this technique, the flow field is decomposed into two fields. The first one is a time-averaged, mean field, whereas the second is a time-dependent, perturbation field. The mean flow is provided by accurate measurements conducted by Trout and McLaughlin (1982) of a supersonic axisymmetric jet (Mach 2.1) that is isentropically expanded. One of the favorable features in the current technique is that the computation of the perturbed field is not very sensitive to the mean one, Idres (1999). Also, perturbed field phase and mean field phase are independent. This gives big amount of freedom in the overall process. For example, the mean flow can be obtained by experiments or by numerical solution of steady governing equations like the steady Navier-Stokes equations or the steady form of the large eddy simulation.

The non-linear effects can not be accounted for in this technique (unlike the direct numerical simulation and the large eddy simulation). As a result of this, the approach may not be valid if the perturbation level is not small enough so that nonlinear effects are limited. However, the far field is known to be linear and much of the physics can be obtained by considering the linear equations. Also, since this technique is based on Euler equations, which neglects viscosity, viscous effects should not be significant. Fortunately, the viscous effects are not important in the considered class of problems because the large-scale dynamics in free shear flows, which are the dominant sound generators in supersonic jets, are essentially inviscid.

The jet properties at the nozzle exit are

Jet / nozzle radius	5 mm	0.197 in
Pressure	5060 N/m ²	150.7 psf
Speed	525 m/s	1722 ft/s
Density	0.1114 Kg/m ³	0.000216 slug/cu ft

In the experiments, hot-wire anemometer was used. However, it cannot be used in conventional high-speed air jets because the dynamic pressures are too big for the fragile probes. That is why a low-density flow is used. Also, the mean flow was excited using a glow-discharge device positioned 2-mm (0.0787 in) from the nozzle exit. The artificially excited measurements were used to explore properties of the coherent-flow structure and its radiated noise. In the current simulation, a small disturbance is introduced at the jet exit, which is assumed to be mainly hydrodynamic (non-propagating) in nature. This disturbance is chosen to represent the applied experimental excitation.

We use the 2-4 McCormack, which is second-order accurate in time and fourth-order accurate in space. It was chosen for its accuracy, speed and simplicity. This scheme has been used in other noise prediction problems and is known to yield accurate results if appropriate boundary conditions are used carefully. The differential operator is split into several one-dimensional operators and applied in a symmetric way to avoid biasing of the solution. One-sided differences are used in the scheme to add dissipation to stabilize the scheme. The boundary conditions are very important in acoustic prediction. Outflow conditions should avoid nonphysical oscillations, which can make the computed solution totally unacceptable. These boundary conditions should allow the acoustic and flow perturbations to leave the computational domain with minimal reflection. The treatment is based on the asymptotic analysis of the linearized equations as given by Tam and Webb (1993). The pressure condition is the same as that obtained by Bayliss and Turkel (1982), Enquest and Majda (1977), and Hariharanand and Hagstrom (1990).

Results

The simulation is performed and the perturbed flow field is computed. For the acoustic field, the pressure perturbation is of special interest because it is used to assess the acoustic field. Audible sound levels vary over a very wide range, and therefore a relative log-scale is typically used to express the sound's intensity. Sound is measured in decibels (dB) where:

$$\text{Sound pressure level (SPL)} = 10 \log \left(\frac{P'_{\text{rms}}}{P'_{\text{Ref}}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where P'_{Ref} is related to the threshold of hearing.

A human whisper involves acoustic intensity of roughly 20 dB, a shout \approx 70 dB, a jackhammer \approx 120 dB, a jet engine at takeoff \approx 170 dB. So, a single modern jet plane at takeoff generates more noise than the combined shouting power of the entire world population. For humans, unprotected exposure to sound levels above 100 dB for more than 15 minutes can cause hearing damage, and permanent hearing loss results from unexpected exposure to sound levels above 110 dB.

Figure 1. Sound pressure levels contours; present study versus experiment

Figure 2. Radial decay of acoustic field in far field

We consider the case of nondimensional frequency of the excitation (or Strouhal number) of 0.2, which is found to be near the most ‘critical’ value at which the plume (i.e. the potential core and the starting mixing layer of the jet) becomes most responsive to excitations. This case also has available experimental results so we can compare with. Figure 1 shows the acoustic field in form of contours of the sound pressure levels. They are compared with the experiments of Trout and McLaughlin (1982). Good agreement is observed. The domain is scaled with the nozzle radius (R_j). In Figure 2, the clarity of the resolved acoustic field is demonstrated. The acoustic field (represented by the normalized root-mean-square of pressure disturbances) must be decaying as a function of $1/r$, whence the sound intensity decays as a function of $(1/r^2)$.

Conclusions

The perturbed and acoustic fields of a supersonic, isentropically expanded free jet were computed using linearized Euler equations. Some comparisons with experimental results suggest the suitability of this technique for this kind of problems. The acoustic field is found to be of constant intensity near the centerline, even after 30 nozzle radii behind the nozzle. Then, there is an increase of the intensity which reaches a peak value before decay starts as a function of $1/r$. These peaks suggest that noise propagates in a directional pattern related to the Mach waves of mean jet flow.

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